

Mechanism of the Formation of 3-Nitro-5-(3'-pyridyl)-Pyrazole from Nicotine

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The yield of 3-nitro-5-(3'-pyridyl) pyrazole, obtained by the oxidation of nicotine with nitric acid, was increased by the addition of sodium nitrite to the reaction mixture. Urea decreased the yield of this pyrazole, which was not obtained by the nitric acid oxidation of cotinine or nornicotine. The pyrazole derived from [1'-¹⁵N]-nicotine was enriched solely on the N-1 nitrogen. A mechanism consistent with these results and related work is presented to explain the formation of this pyrazole derivative.

IN 1931 it was reported¹ that the oxidation of nicotine with concentrated nitric acid yields mainly nicotinic acid and about 5% of a pyrazole derivative. It was originally suggested that this minor product was 4-nitro-5-(3'-pyridyl) pyrazole. This structure was shown to be incorrect by Lund², and proven to be 3-nitro-5-(3'-pyridyl) pyrazole (XI) by Clemo and Holmes³. We⁴ utilized this reaction in a degradation of [2',5'-¹⁴C]-nicotine derived from [2-¹⁴C] ornithine. Activity at C-5' of nicotine could be determined by difference since this pyrazole derivative contains all the carbons of nicotine except C-5' and the N-methyl group. The present article describes experiments carried out to elucidate the mechanism of the formation of this pyrazole derivative. We considered that the N-2 nitrogen of the pyrazole nucleus is derived from nitrous acid generated during the nitric acid oxidation. In support of this, we discovered that the addition of sodium nitrite to the oxidation mixture increased the yield of XI to 8-9%. Furthermore the addition of urea (a nitrous acid scavenger) dramatically reduced the yield of XI (0.8%). Examination of the crude oxidation mixture by TLC revealed the presence of cotinine (VII), as well as nicotine, nicotinic acid, and the pyrazole derivative. We thus considered cotinine as a plausible intermediate between nicotine and XI. However treatment of cotinine with concentrated nitric acid in the presence, or absence of sodium nitrite, failed to yield any of the pyrazole.

The origin of the nitrogens of the pyrazole ring was determined by carrying out the oxidation of [1'-¹⁵N] nicotine⁵. The ¹⁵N content of the nicotine and the resultant pyrazole was determined by mass spectrometry (29/28 ratio) on the nitrogen gas produced by a modified Dumas determination⁶ on these compounds. The excess ¹⁵N content of the nicotine (the average of the pyridine nitrogen (0%) and the pyrrolidine nitrogen) was 47.6%. The pyrazole derivative, which contains four nitrogens, had an excess ¹⁵N of 23.5%, a result consistent with complete retention of the ¹⁵N originally present at the 1'-position of nicotine. The location of

the ¹⁵N in the pyrazole was deduced by examination of the fragments produced by electron impact mass spectrometry on the pyrazole. The Table lists some of the most abundant fragments derived from the unenriched pyrazole, and material derived from [1'-¹⁵N] nicotine. The structures of these fragments (illustrated in Figure 2) were deduced from previous work on the mass spectrometry and fragmentation of pyrazoles⁷⁻¹⁰. It is clear from this data that the ¹⁵N in the enriched material was all located at the N-1 position.

The N-methyl group of nicotine is essential for pyrazole formation since nornicotine with concentrated nitric acid did not yield any of the pyrazole. It has been shown that tertiary amines react with nitrous acid to yield N-nitrosium compounds which eliminate HNO (which dimerizes to N₂O and water) affording iminium salts which then undergo hydrolysis to secondary amines and a carbonyl compound¹¹.

We thus propose that the pyrazole XI is produced by the mechanism illustrated in Figure 1. Elimination of HNO from the nitrosium salt of nicotine (II) affords the pyrrolinium salt III. Hydration of this iminium salt, and oxidation of the resultant carbinolamine yields

TABLE—MASS SPECTROMETRY OF 3-NITRO-5-(3'-PYRIDYL) PYRAZOLE (XI)

Unenriched XI m/e (relative intensity)	Structure	¹⁵ N-Enriched XI m/e (relative intensity)
190 (100)	XI	191 (100)
118 (17.1)	XIII	119 (15.0)
105 (8.7)	XIV	106 (6.1)
78 (18.9)	XV	78 (18.0)

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Fig. 1 : Formation of Pyrazoles from Nicotine by the Action of Nitrous Acid.

Fig. 2 : Structures of the Fragments Obtained by Mass Spectrometry of 3-Nitro-5-(3'-pyridyl) pyrazole.

cotinine (VII). The production of cotinine by the enzymatic¹², and mercuric acetate¹³ oxidation of nicotine is also considered to proceed via the iminium salt III. It is suggested that the iminium salt III, or its open chain amino-aldehyde undergoes C-nitrosation at C-4', and N-nitrosation on the secondary amine to yield VI, in which the C-nitroso group is depicted as the tautomeric oxime. A plausible cyclization then yields V. The nitroso group is then oxidized to a nitro, and the aldehyde to a carboxyl, affording IX. A concerted decarboxylation and dehydration then yield the pyrazoline X. The oxidative N-demethylation of aromatic amines such as dimethylaniline during nitration is a common phenomenon¹⁴. This is considered to occur in the final step leading to XI, which also involves dehydrogenation of the ring to yield a pyrazole. In support of this tentative mechanism it has been recently reported¹⁵ that one of the products of the nitrosation of nicotine is 4-(N-methyl-N-nitrosoamino)-4-(3'-pyridyl) butanal (IV), presumably formed by ring opening of III followed by N-nitrosation of the secondary amino group. It was also found that excess

nitrite under more severe conditions (90°C) resulted in the formation of 1-methyl-5-(3'-pyridyl) pyrazole(XII), which was probably formed via compound VIII. This series of reactions is thus analogous to the ones that we propose for the formation of XI. We do not consider that XII is a precursor of XI, since Lund² showed that the nitration of 5-(3'-pyridyl) pyrazole yielded the isomeric 4-nitro-5-(3'-pyridyl) pyrazole.

Experimental

General methods: Melting points are corrected. The ¹⁵N analyses and other mass spectra were determined by Adrian Swanson and his assistants at the University of Minnesota using an Hitachi-Perkin Elmer RMU-6D mass spectrometer. UV spectra were determined on a Cary 11 spectrophotometer.

Oxidation of nicotine with nitric acid: Nicotine (1.62 g, 10 mmol) was added to concentrated nitric acid (10 ml) and the solution was heated on a steam bath for 16 hr. The pale yellow solution was then evaporated to dryness *in vacuo*. TLC of a portion of the residue on alumina GF-254 (Merck) developing with a mixture of methanol and chloroform (1:4) indicated the presence of four compounds (detected by UV-light and I₂ vapor). These compounds had R_f values of 0.92, 0.85, 0.55, and 0.0, corresponding to nicotine, cotinine, 3-nitro-5-(3'-pyridyl) pyrazole, and nicotinic acid, respectively. This crude reaction mixture was dissolved in water (10 ml) and the solution brought to pH 5 by the addition of NaOH. A yellow crystalline precipitate separated, which was dried and sublimed (180°C, 5 × 10⁻⁴ mm) affording the pyrazole XI (84 mg, 4.4%).

m.p. 275-276°C (lit⁴. m.p. 277-278°C), UV λ_{max} (ϵ) (in 0.1 N HCl) 222 (15,100), 253 (17,000), 275 (11,600), shoulder nm. Mass spectrum m/e (relative intensity) : 191 (13.7), 190 (100), 118 (17.1), 116 (14.6), 114 (metastable), 105 (8.7), 104 (6.3), 103 (8.2), 90 (8.9), 88 (6.6), 78 (18.9), 77 (5.5), 76 (7.1).

When the oxidation was carried out with the same amount of nicotine in the presence of sodium nitrite (1.6 g, 23 mmol) the yield of the pyrazole in three separate experiments was 165, 179, and 191 mg, representing an average yield of 9.4%.

Oxidation in the presence of urea (1.4 g, 23 mmol) resulted in the formation of the pyrazole XI in yields of 1.5, 3.0, and 0.5 mg, representing an average yield of 0.8%.

Oxidation of cotinine and nornicotine with nitric acid: Cotinine (1.0 g, 5.7 mmol) and sodium nitrite (0.8 g, 11.6 mmol) were oxidized with nitric acid (10 ml) as previously described for the oxidation of nicotine. A UV spectrum of the crude reaction mixture did not reveal the presence of any of the pyrazole XI. A similar oxidation of nornicotine gave similar results.

Oxidation of [1'-¹⁵N] nicotine with nitric acid: [1'-¹⁵N]-Nicotine diperchlorate (531 mg) was oxidized with nitric acid in the presence of sodium nitrite as previously described affording [1-¹⁵N]-3-nitro-5-(3'-pyridyl) pyrazole (23 mg, 8.2%).

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